

Assessment Of The Teacher's Qualification And Utilization Of Instructional Materials In The Implementation Of Primary Schools Islamic Studies Curriculum In North-West Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria

¹MUSA Faruk Jega; ²ALTINE Abdullahi & ³MUHAMMAD Lukman

^{1,2&3} Primary Education Department

Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto, Nigeria

lukupcy@gmail.com/08034500112

ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the implementation of the Islamic Studies curriculum in primary schools within the Northwest Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Specifically, it examines the qualifications of teachers and the types of instructional materials used in the delivery of the curriculum. The research focuses on two primary questions: the qualifications of Islamic Studies teachers and the types of instructional materials used in teaching. The study utilizes a descriptive survey design, targeting Islamic Studies teachers, headteachers, and supervisors in selected public primary schools across Sokoto, Kano, Katsina, and Kebbi states. Data were collected through surveys with 240 respondents, including teachers and head-teachers. The findings revealed that the majority of Islamic Studies teachers held the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) in Islamic Studies, which was the highest qualification among the respondents. Regarding instructional materials, the study found that a variety of resources were used, including cardboard papers for Arabic alphabets, copies of the Qur'an, natural creations for teaching Tawhid, and items for teaching ablution and prayer. However, some materials, such as videos for teaching congregational prayer and Hajj, were less frequently used. The study concludes that, while teachers generally have the appropriate qualifications and utilize a range of instructional materials, there are gaps in the use of modern audiovisual aids. Based on these findings, recommendations are made to enhance teacher qualifications, improve the availability of instructional materials, and ensure regular quality assurance inspections for effective curriculum implementation.

Keywords: Islamic Studies, teacher qualifications, instructional materials, primary schools, Northwest Nigeria, curriculum implementation.

INTRODUCTION

Islamic Studies as a subject is taught in schools operating at various levels of educations in Nigeria. Specifically, Islamic Studies as a subject was introduced in the Nigerian Educational Curriculum in both primary and post-primary schools by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), (Muhamamd, 2018). Islamic Studies as a subject is meant to train pupils in such a manner that their attitude to life, actions, decisions and approaches to all kinds of knowledge are governed by the spiritual and deeply entrenched ethical values of Islam (Araniri, 2020). Similarly, Islamic Studies, as viewed by Habibah (2015) deals with implementation, learning, training, drills and researches about Islam. On the other hand, Islamic Education may be referred to as a process by which the values spelt out in the Qur'an and the tradition of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) are

handed down from generation to generation (Fadhillah,2020). Islamic Studies is learnt as a classroom subject in Nigeria. The National Policy cherishes and promotes, among other things, moral and spiritual values in interpersonal human relations. Such values are clearly spelt out and emphasized in the various branches of Islamic Studies taken by students (Araniri, (2020).

Implementation is an activity aimed at bringing about meaningful learning through a method that is morally and pedagogically acceptable. Meaningful implementation cannot take place without a professionally qualified teacher and a method that takes account of learners' individual differences. In the same vein, implementation is a relational work that involves concerted actions of at least two people, the teacher, who impacts knowledge, and the student who receives the knowledge (Agung, 2021). However, for the process of implementation to be successful, the teachers must know more than the pupils to establish a knowledge gradient that will make the flow of information go from an area of high concentration of knowledge to an area of low concentration of knowledge. The body of the knowledge meant for learning must be structured in a way that would facilitate learning and the presentation of the body of knowledge to the learners should follow both logical order and psychological order, to achieve the most effective sequence (Agung, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum in Primary Schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria. However, the specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the qualifications status of teachers used in the implementation Islamic Studies curriculum in primary schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria;
2. Determine the kinds of instructional materials used in the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum in primary schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria;

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the qualifications statuses of teachers used in the implementation Islamic Studies curriculum in primary schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria?
2. What are the kinds of instructional materials used in the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum in primary schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria?

Significance of the Study

The researcher believes that assessing the implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum at the primary school level would be of significance in many ways to the primary school head teachers, teachers, school monitoring officers, the Arabic and Islamic Education Board and the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB). In the first place, head teachers would benefit from this study as its findings would equip them with the importance of carrying out internal instructional supervision or regular basis to ensure effective implementation of Islamic Studies and others subjects as well. Secondly, classroom teachers in primary schools, specifically those implementing Islamic Studies, would benefit from this study as its findings would reveal to them the effect of instructional materials and how to utilize them in the classrooms for effective instructional delivery.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The research is intended to assess the implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum in public primary schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria. There are many factors that influence the implementation of curriculum specifically, the study covered teachers' qualifications and instructional materials. The subjects for the study were Islamic Studies teachers, head teachers and supervisors in public primary schools in the study area. The Zone covered four (4) states namely: Sokoto, Kano, Katsina, and Kebbi. The study covered some selected teachers of Islamic Studies, Head teachers and supervisors in some selected LGEAs primary schools in the study area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study was about understanding the concept of Curriculum, Concept of Islamic Studies, objectives of Islamic studies in primary schools in Nigeria, Implementation Qualification and Experience Required in Teachers for Implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum at the Primary Schools Level in Nigeria and Method of Implementation Islamic Studies in Primary schools is reviewed.

Concept of Curriculum

For most lay men, curriculum today is equated with course guides, syllabi or textbooks that establish the course. Such a classic definition of the term also reflects the meaning of curriculum for the most conservatives or structured educationists in the field. Walton et al (1976) in Ben-Yunusa (2008), defines curriculum as that content and those processes designed to bring about learning of education value. By this definition, curriculum was considered to include both what was to be taught and by what means it was to be taught.

According to Block (1998), in Yusuf (2012), curriculum is a prescribed body of knowledge and methods which can be communicated. According to this definition, any knowledge which specifies the channels, means or procedures that knowledge can be taught, is referred to as curriculum. Curriculum is, therefore, the sum total of all planned and unplanned activities which learners are exposed to in a school setting.

However, it must be borne in mind that, a curriculum cannot be limited to the children's immediate interest in school. Their interest must be organized in terms of social values. The school only serves as a mere agency of social control expected to cater for the long-range behavior changes of the society which the above definitions of the concept of curriculum failed to specify.

Concept of Islam and Islamic Studies

Islam is from an Arabic word "Salam" which means "Submissions". Islam points to the fundamental religious creed which dictates that none is worthy of worship except Allah. Maigari (2006) viewed Islamic studies as the totality of learning experiences, which center on the relationship between human being and his Creator and between man and his fellow men. According to the Islam, Allah is the only creator and owns the universe and is the creator of everything (Al-attas, 2005).

Agung, (2021) expressed that; it is Islam when an individual totally submits to the will of that One God (Allah) conforming inwardly and outwardly to His laws. Islam guides (man) to the dictates of the Glorious Qur'an and the principles of the messenger, Prophet Muhammad (SAW). Islam is a form of discipline and guidance oriented in all human affairs, individual and communal, spiritual and material; economic and political, legal and cultural, intellectual; and national and global interaction in human sphere.

Objectives of Islamic Studies in Primary Schools in Nigeria

The primary aim of Islamic studies is to give the world a philosophy with a standard of values and judgment that applies to all spheres and activities of human life. This was further confirmed by Islamic educationists like Imam al Ghazali and others who believed that unless the philosophy succeeds in broadening its range of application and given Islamic concepts for all branches of knowledge, it will not be able to satisfy the new generation and save them from invasion of divided purposes of any paralyzing doubts. According to Bagheni (2001), the aims and objectives of Islamic Studies include:

1. Recognition of Allah as the creator and sustainer of the universe and the sole source of values;
2. Cultivating the sense of gratitude to Allah and submission to His guidance and moral law, both in our worship to Him and our behaviour towards out fellow men;
3. Awakening of the faculty of intellect and reasoning in accordance with the Glorious Qur'an injunctions which says "will you not use reason and with you not ponder and reflect;
4. Encouragement of the pursuit of useful knowledge in accordance with the saying of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) "Their search or knowledge is a duty for every Muslim male or female and the application of such knowledge for the benefit of humanity in the field of science, technology, medicine and so on;
5. Attainment of balanced development of the individual and community by giving due weight to the physical, social, intellectual, moral and spiritual needs of man;
6. Awakening in the heart the consciousness of the presence of Allah as a witness of our action, thought and behavior, acting as a restraint on wrong doing whether public or private and as an incentive to good behavior.

Qualifications Required for Teachers in the Implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum at Primary Schools Level in Nigeria

Qualified Islamic Studies teachers are conceptualized as Islamic Studies teachers having the ability to produce the desired results using the appropriate materials and suitable methods in dealing with the students and, at the same time, having good understanding of the subject matter of Islamic Studies. Ehiozuwa (2005) in Gyallesu (2016) found that there was a positive relationship between the teacher's levels of training on pupils academic achievements. This was from his studies on the influence of teacher's level of professional training on pupils' academic performance. Edozie (2005) asserted that the problem with primary and secondary education in Nigeria is the large percentage of teachers that are incompetent, that is, they are not qualified and experienced. He added that there was also the problem of too many pupils per teacher in many schools.

Instructional Materials Used in the Implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum

Instructional materials are defined by Alebiosu (2005) as, those things that a teacher uses to help students in their learning. These include books, charts, texts, manuals, audio-visual aids, artifacts and other archaeological materials. On the role of curriculum materials in curriculum implementation, Adejabu (2000) stated that, curriculum materials if creatively, efficiently and effectively used, will enhance learning, improve teachers' competence and also make learning more meaningful. She further added that these materials stimulate learners' interest, take care of a wide audience and make learning become more concrete, real and immediate. Adesina and Adetero (2002) declared that without adequate tools even the best teacher is handicapped. They added that the room itself must be conducive to the learning that is expected of the pupils.

Materials in Islamic Studies are necessary for a successful implementation-learning process. It should be noted that there is no topic in Islamic Studies that will not require the use of instructional materials. These resources or materials are very vital instructional inputs to facilitate and direct pupils' attention to achieve the desired learning outcomes. In a nutshell, learning resources presents opportunities for good implementation as well as sound and effective learning.

Theoretical Framework

There are lots of theories related to this study. But the researcher has based the study upon Systems Approach Theory (SAT) by Beftalanffy (1967).

Systems Approach Theory (SAT) of Beftalanffy (1967)

In a systems approach theory interrelated elements interact together towards a common goal. This theory states that in every system there are three elements involved to attain a goal. Inputs, transformational process (activities) and outputs (the intended results or outcomes). For implementation process of educational programme there must be inputs of human and material resources. There must also be activities (implementation) and outputs to make value judgment of effectiveness. Therefore the researcher finds the theory relevant and suitable for the study.

The features of Systems Approach Theory of input, process and output were considered in analyzing the role of participants, stakeholders and elements such as learners, teachers, head teachers and supervisors in the State Universal Basic Education Board in the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

The purpose of this research was to find out the assessment of the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum in public primary schools of Northwest Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria. In this aspect, empirical studies which bore relevance to the present study were reviewed. The reviews cut across two levels of schoolings i.e. primary and post primary. There were many related researches conducted on such topic. Examples of the researches are provided in the page that follows.

Studies on Qualification of Teachers Implementation Islamic Studies Curriculum in Primary Schools.

Enyi and Ikenazor (2023) carried out a study titled Teacher Qualifications and Competencies in the Effective Implementation of Basic Science and Technology Curriculum in Schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. This paper investigated the competency gaps of basic science teachers in implementation the basic science and technology curriculum. To guide the study, one research question was posed and

answered and one null hypothesis was tested at $P < 0.05$ level significance. The study was a descriptive survey. The study was carried out in Enugu state, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 306 basic science teachers and 135 science teacher educators. The sample for the study consisted of 148 respondents. Two instruments were used for data collection. The instruments included Basic Science Teachers Competency Needs Questionnaire (BSTCNQ), and Basic Science Teachers' Competencies Observational Rating Scale (BSTCORS). The BSTCORS had inter-rater reliability index of 0.97. There was one research question and one hypothesis. The research question was answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypothesis was tested using t-test statistics at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Results showed that all the competencies listed in BSTCNQ were assessed to be needed by BS teachers for implementation the Basic Science Curriculum and that there was no significant difference in the mean rating scores of Basic Science teachers and science teacher-educators on competencies needed for implementation the Basic Science Curriculum. The educational implications of the findings of the study were highlighted and recommendations were proffered that stakeholders in basic education should provide funds and appropriate human resources for organizing in-service training BS teachers to enhance their competencies and effectiveness in implementation of Basic Science.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

A descriptive survey design was used for conducting the study. This design involved collecting and analyzing of data. This design was considered appropriate for this study as it helped the researcher to obtain relevant information required by collecting data that helps to describe how adequate instructional materials and teacher's qualification for the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum were used. Again, this design was considered suitable for this study because it enabled the researcher to obtain facts and figures needed, in which the results of the analysis would be used for decision taking and generalization.

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/No	States	Number of Islamic Studies Teachers	Number of supervisors	Total
1	Sokoto	276	31	399
2	Kano	115	12	160
3	Katsina	155	15	201
4	Kebbi	252	28	264
	Total	798	86	1,024

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The population of the study comprises Islamic Studies teachers, head teachers and supervisors in public primary schools in Northwest Geopolitical Zone.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Table 2: Sample of the Study

S/No	Local Government	Number of Islamic Studies Teachers	Number of supervisors	Total
1	Sokoto	44	6	50
2	Kano	40	6	46
3	Katsina	43	6	49
4	Kebbi	38	5	43
	Total	240	34	274

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The sample size of the study consisted of 274 respondents which comprised 240 Islamic Studies teachers, 20 head teachers and 14 supervisors selected based on Research Advisor (2006) table for determining sample size from a given population. Simple random sampling was used to select a total of 20 public primary schools and 240 Islamic Studies teachers for the study. The justification for using the random sampling was to give each school and its Islamic Studies teachers an equal chance of being selected to participate in the study. The distribution of sample is displayed in Table 2.

Research Question One: *What is the qualification status of teacher's implementation Islamic Studies Curriculum in primary schools in Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.?*

Table 3: Respondents' Responses on the Status of Teachers' Qualifications

S/No.	QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Senior Secondary School Certificate (SSSC)	20	8.3
2.	National Diploma (N.D Islamic Studies)	40	16.7
3.	Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE Islamic Studies)	120	50.0
4.	Bachelor of Arts Degree (Islamic Studies)	24	10.0
5.	Bachelor of Education Degree (Islamic Studies)	26	10.8
6	Master of Education Degree (Islamic Studies)	10	4.2
TOTAL		240	100

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 3 shows the qualifications possessed by the respondents. From Table 3 it appeared that a total of 120 respondents (representing 50%) of the entire respondents were in possession of the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) in Islamic Studies as their highest qualification. Similarly, 40 respondents (representing 16.7%) had National Diploma (N.D.) in Islamic Studies as their highest qualification. However, only 10 respondents (representing 4.2%) were found to have possessed Master of Education Degree (Islamic Studies) as their highest qualification. Therefore, based on the 50% bench mark decision rule, it was obvious that in terms of qualification status of teachers, the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) in Islamic Studies which attracted 50% of the total responses was the highest qualification possessed by majority of teachers of Islamic Studies. Consequently, this was an indication that teachers of Islamic Studies had the right implementation qualifications required for the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum at the primary school level.

Research Question Two: *What are the kinds of instructional materials used in the implementation of Islamic Studies in primary schools in Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.?*

Table 4: Respondents' Responses on Kind of Instructional Materials Used in Implementation Islamic Studies
N = 240

S/N		SA/A	%	SD/D	%	Remarks
1	Teachers used Cardboard papers on which the Arabic alphabet were boldly written in implementation pupils Arabic alphabets.	208	86.7	32	13.3	Agree
2	Teachers used materials such as Flash cards, recorded cassettes, CD, DVD Recorder, Radio and MP in implementation pupils Arabic alphabet.	154	65	86	35	Agree
3	Teachers used Copies of Glorious Qur'an with Arabic text and translations in implementation pupils Surah of the Glorious Qur'an.	236	98.3	4	1.7	Agree
4	Teachers of Islamic Studies used natural creations of Allah and their Pictures such as sun, moon, stars and rivers in implementation pupils Tawhid.	240	100	0	0	Agree
5	Teachers used kettles of pure water, hand washing basins and bowls of pure water in implementation ablution.	230	95.8	10	4.2	Agree
6	Teachers used Mosques, mats or Carpets in implementation prayer (Salat).	228	95	12	5	Agree
7	Teachers used video of congregational prayer, recorded Iqamah on cassette and recorded At-Tashahhud on cassette in implementation congregational prayer.	100	41.7	140	58.3	Disagree
8	Materials for performing Tayammum such as stones, sand, gravels were used in implementation Tayammum in the classroom.	221	95	19	5	Agree
9	Pictures, video clips showing Makkah, Madinah, the Kaabah, Hajaratul-Aswad and Cave of Hira were used in schools to teach Hajj pilgrimage.	94	39.2	146	60.8	Disagree
10	Teachers use maps of the places of battles between Muslims and non-Muslims during the period of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) to teach pupils the history of Islam.	168	70	72	30	Agree

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 4 above shows the kinds of instructional materials used in implementation Islamic Studies curriculum in primary schools in Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria. Specifically, majority of the respondents (86.7%) confirmed that teachers used cardboard papers with inscription of Arabic alphabet to teach pupils. Similarly, 65% of the teachers and head-teachers acknowledged that teachers used materials such as flash cards, recorded cassettes, CD, DVD recorders, radio and MP while 98.3% of the respondents confirmed that teachers used copies of the Qur'an to teach pupils selected Surah from Qur'an. All the respondents (100%) agreed that Islamic Studies teachers used natural creation of Allah and their pictures such as sun, moon, stars and rivers in implementation Islamic Studies. About 95% to 95.8% of the respondents confirmed that teachers taught relevant Islamic Studies topics with the use of mats, carpets, kettles of water, hand washing basins and bowls.

The majority of the respondents (58.3%) disagreed that teachers used video of congregational prayer, recorded Iqamah and At-Tashahhud on cassette in implementation congregation prayers. Large numbers of the respondents (95%) agreed that teachers taught pupils Tayammum with materials such as stones, sand and gravels practically and 70% of the respondents confirmed that teachers used maps to teach Islamic History but 60.8% of the respondents disagreed that teachers used video clips for implementation Islam in historical places during hajji pilgrimage. It was however very clear that the use of pictures, video clips by teachers to show important places of ibadah during Hajj (pilgrimage) were very rare as only 39.2% of the respondents agreed to the statement. Therefore, based on the 50% bench mark decision rule, it was obvious that Islamic Studies teachers did utilize various kinds of instructional materials in implementation the subject. This had therefore indicated that the extent to which Islamic Studies teachers used various instructional materials was adequate for the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum at the primary school level.

CONCLUSION

In view of the findings of the study, the researcher concluded as follows. Teachers of Islamic Studies had the right implementation qualifications required for the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum. Also, the Instructional materials were found to be appropriate for the implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum in Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria. However, majority of the supervisors were not from Islamic Studies but related disciplines (subjects). Also, a high level of difficulty of some topics experienced by the pupils at primary school level was also noted.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been given:

1. There is a need for the provision of the qualified and competent teachers to teach Islamic Studies in primary schools of Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.
2. Government, non-governmental organizations, philanthropists, parents and old boys should help provide instructional materials such as radios, tape recorders, CD players for Qur'an recitation, projectors and videos to aid pupils learn on their own and at their own pace in studying of Islamic Studies.
3. Quality assurance inspection exercise by competent personnel with background in Islamic Studies should be regularly conducted to help check teachers' performances and learners' problems in public primary schools of Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria and Nigeria as a whole.

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